

Content Marketing

R. Vasinagalakshmi & T. Sangeetha

M.Com (CA), Department of Commerce

Nadar Saraswathi College of Arts and Science Theni, Tamil Nadu

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month:

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Vasinagalakshmi, R.
“Content Marketing.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 7, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 227–30.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3451702](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451702)

Abstract

Content marketing is a form of selling focused on creating, publishing, and distributing content for a targeted audience of On line.

- *To Attract attention and generate leads*
- *To Expand their customer base*
- *To Generate or increase online sales*
- *To Increase brand awareness or credibility*
- *To Engage an on-line community of users*

There will always be steps and process through which you have to go to active your goals and targets. You simply cannot hope to achieve your goals and targets by not doing anything or hoping that someone else will do it for you.

Introduction

Content Marketing

Content marketing Involves creating high-quality content. And it is distributing that content across different venues. This content should be Educational; it should answer a question or fulfill a need for its intended reader or watcher. Companies that practice content selling aim to become a trusted source of useful information, thus proving themselves as professionals on topics relevant to their stocks or services.

Mr. Barker will also need to produce content about depression, trauma, and other mood-related issues. Articles or blog posts about how spending time with dogs can improve mood and alleviate depressive symptoms would also be relevant to doggy dopamine; this material would appeal to visitors during a later stage of the buyer’s journey, a topic I’ll discuss in this the material would appeal to visitors during a later stage of the buyer’s journey, a topic I’ll discuss in greater detail later.

History

Traditional marketers have long related content to disseminate information about a brand and build a brand’s reputation. Taking advantage of technological advancements in transport and communication, business owners started to apply content marketing techniques in the late 19th century. They also attempted to build connections with their customers. For Example:

In 1732, Benjamin franklin issued the poor Richard’s Almanack to promote his printing business.

In 1895, John Deere launched magazine the furrow providing information to farmers on how to becomes more active. The magazine, considered the first custom publication, is still in circulation, giving 1.5 million readers in 40 countries in 12 different languages.

In 1900, Michelin received the Michelin Guide, offering drivers information on auto maintain, accommodation, and other travel tips. 35000 copies were given for free in this first edition

In 1904, jell-o sales men went door-to-door, distribution their cookbook for free. Touting the dessert as a ready food, the company saw its traffic rise to over \$1 million by 1906.

Common Metrics

Metrics to determine the success of content marketing are often tied to the original goals of the campaign.

For example, for each of these aims, a content marketer may measure the different engagement and conversion metrics:

Brand Awareness and Visinility

Business focused on expanding their reach to more customers will want to pay attention to the in cress in a volume of visitors, as well as the quality of those interactions. Traditional measures of volume include the number of visitors to a page and number of emails collected, while time spent on page and click-through to other pages/ photos are good indicators for engagement.

Number of visitors to a paged Time spent on the page

Click-through photos/ across pages/Number of emails collected

Brand Health Metrics

Businesses want to include the impact that their messages have on consumers. Brand strength refers to the positive or negative feedback that a business gets. It also includes how important a brand is for customers. With these companies want to find out if brand character influences their consumers to make a purchase.

Measures in this Part Comprise

Share of voice (sov) is the number of times a brand has been told versus its competitors (conversations). Out side the digital world, sov stands for space and frequency a brand advertisement is placed on conventional media sentiment is when the brand has negative, positive, or neutral feed back.

Brand influence refers to the number of items a post, comment, or tweet is shared on different platforms.

Diversified User Base

A business hoping to reach not only more but also new type of customers online, they should pay heed to the demographics of new companies, as evidenced by cookies that can be installed, different on-line behaviors, and different buying habits of on line visitors.

- Differences in buying patterns a user behavior of visitors sources of traffic(i.e., SEO, social media, referral, direct)
- Demographics of visitors
- sources of traffic (i.e., SEO, referral, social media, direct)

Implications

The rise of content marketing has turned much traditional business into media publishing companies for example

- red bull, which sells a high-energy behavior, has published youtube videos, hosted experience, and sponsored events around extreme sports and actions like mountain biking, BMX, snowboarding, motocross, cliff-diving, skateboarding, freestyle motocross and method 1 racing red bull that “produces full-length feature films for cinema and downstream channels (DVD, video, TV) is an international monthly magazine red bull publishes with a focus on men’s sports culture and life style

Content mapping based on the customer journey: Have you heard of content mapping before

- If you haven’t about time that you do
- it’s remarkably valuable and important for your content marketing strategy
- content mapping is the act of understanding your audience so well that you can then plan content for each stage of their journey toward buying your products
- As you well know, fewer people go straight from discovery to buying

Combination of the Supply Chain and the user’s Experience

The supply chain of digital content marketing mainly consists of commercial stakeholders and end-user stakeholder, which represent content providers and distribution and customers separately. In this process, distribution manage the interface between the publisher and the consumer the distribution could identify the content that consumers need through external channels and implement marketing strategies for example library and document supply companies as intermediates can deliver the digital content of e-book and e-journal articles to the users according to their search results through the electronic channels another example is when consumer pay for the acquisition of some mp3 downloads search engines can be used to identify different music providers and smart tools can be user by consumers to examine for multiple song provider sites in a word the digital content marketing method needs to be conducted at the business level needs to be conducted at the business Interaction with the consumer through electronic service:

Electronic services refer to interactive network service in the electronic services the interaction between the customer and the organizations mainly through network technologies such as using e-mail telephone online chat windows for communication.

Digital Content Marketing

Digital content marketing which is a management method uses digital products through different electronic channels to identify forecast and satisfy the need of the customers it must be consistently maintained to preserve or change the behavior of customers.

Examples

On March 6, 2012, dollar shave club launched their on-line videos campaign. In the first 48 hours of their videos debuting on you tube, they had over 12000 people signing up for the service. The video cost just \$4500 to make than 21million views. The videos were considered as one of the best viral marketing campaigns of 2012 and won best out of nowhere videos campaign at the 2012 Ad Age viral video Awards.

The big word project, launched in 2008 aimed to redefine the Oxford English Dictionary by allowing people to present their website as the meaning of their favored word. The project creates to fund two Masters students educations attracted the attention of bloggers worldwide, and was emphasized on daring fireball and wired magazine.

In mid 2016, an Indian tea company has delivered 6000 tea bags to Donald Trump and launched a video content on youtube and face book. The videos campaign received various awards including most creating pr stunt in southeast alas after receiving videos share 3.1 m videos view in first 72 hour and hundredths of publication mentions across 80 countries.

Conclusion

Now Mr. barker understands how to get started with content marketing, and hopefully you do too there still so much to learn, thought, so why don't you check out some of inkling's content marketing blog posts if you like what you read, don't hesitate to give us a shout on twitter or face book we always love to hear from you.

References

1. <https://www.weebly.com>.
2. <https://www.inklyo.com>.
3. <https://neilpatel.com> <https://en.m.wikipedia.org>.